

Measuring the occupants' well-being in the built environment: towards the integration of physiological and environmental parameters in a multidomain BIM-based platform

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Abstract—There is increasing interest in developing multidomain monitoring systems for the built environment, covering not only structural health-related aspects but also focusing on environmental and physiological parameters directly determining the occupants' comfort and well-being. Integrating this information in the Building Information Modelling (BIM) of a building makes the whole ecosystem interconnected, thus providing a feedforward loop capable of improving people's well-being as well as building energy consumption. This paper presents the preliminary results of the solution proposed within the framework of the European project MULTICLIMACT, seeking tools enhancing resilience at multiple scale levels. Results prove the feasibility and the efficiency of the proposed approach to integrate data from a plethora of multidomain sensors in a flexible, modular, and interoperable manner.

Keywords—well-being, built environment, monitoring platform, data fusion, physiological parameters, environmental parameters

I. INTRODUCTION

The assessment of well-being in the built environment is fundamental to promptly act in terms of thermo-hygrometric control due to the mutual interference between well-being, human productivity, and subject's health status [1–3]. In fact,

not only environmental quantities like air temperature, relative humidity, and air velocity determine comfort and well-being, but also the subjective physiological reactions of the occupant, of which several can be quantitatively characterized through physiological measurements (e.g., heart rate, HR, and related variability) [4,5]. However, the assessment of well-being is not straightforward at all, also considering the complexity already presented within its definition [6]. Nevertheless, measuring well-being within educational environments like schools, academic institutions, and libraries could help those occupants particularly vulnerable to the indoor environmental quality. Ensuring Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ) in these environments is pivotal, also with a view of energy efficiency [7,8]. Different thermal conditions undoubtedly affect concentration and attention levels, as well as overall well-being; Turunen et al. [9] evidenced that noise and stuffy air/poor IEQ are the main factors causing inconveniences like fatigue and headache. Adaptive behaviours and perceived control [7] surely represent relevant tools in this context, enabling humans to effectively adapt to a certain thermal environment also in compliance with social conventions. However, it is worthy to note that human perception is subjective and is affected also by the thermal history of the subject and many other factors [10]; this means that different occupants of a same room can differently perceive thermal

as the use of personal comfort tools (e.g., space heater) were allowed according to the subjects' needs.

B. Sensors for data acquisition

Environmental sensors were installed in the living environment as reported in Fig. 1. The employed sensors and the respective measured quantities are reported in Table I together with sensors technical specifications. Concerning multidomain physiological measurements, a smartband (MAXREFDES104, Analog Devices, Norwood, MA, United States, Fig. 2) was worn by the participants for the whole test period on their dominant wrist; at present, up to 5 subjects could be monitored simultaneously through personal sensors sending data to the same platform. The sensor specifications and the measured parameters are reported in Table II.

C. Integration of data in the monitoring platform

As mentioned above, both environmental and physiological parameters were integrated in a digital platform developed by LIS (Live Information System, Ancona, Italy). The platform interacts with sensors using internal REST APIs developed by LIS. Data is measured by sensors every 5 s and sent to API using a JSON format.

D. Surveys

Different types of surveys were administered at the middle (i.e., lunchtime) and at the end of each day to the test participants.

Fig. 2 MaxRefDes104 smartband worn on wrist.

TABLE I. TECHNICAL SPECIFICATIONS OF ENVIRONMENTAL SENSORS

Sensor type	Model	Specifications
Air temperature (T) sensor	DHT22	Operating range: -40~80 °C Accuracy: $\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ Resolution: 0.1 °C Repeatability: $\pm 0.2^\circ\text{C}$
Relative humidity (RH) sensor	DHT22	Operating range: 0-100% Accuracy: $\pm 2\%$ Resolution: 0.1% Repeatability: $\pm 1\%$ Humidity hysteresis: $\pm 0.3\%$ Long-term stability: $\pm 0.5\%/year$
CO ₂ sensor	SGP30	Operating range: 400 – 60000 ppm Resolution: 1-31 ppm (depending on subranges) Sampling rate: 1 Hz
PM2.5 sensor	SPS30	Precision: $\pm 10 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ / $\pm 10\%$ m.v above $100 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ Sampling rate: 40 Hz
VOC sensor	SGP30	Operating range: 0 – 60000 ppb Resolution: 1-32 ppb (depending on subranges) Sampling rate: 1 Hz

TABLE II. TECHNICAL SPECIFICATIONS OF MAXREFDES104

Sensor type	Model	Measured quantity	Specifications
PPG	MAX 86176	PPG signal (from which Heart Rate, HR, and oxygen saturation, SpO ₂ , can be derived)	LED current: <math>< 128\text{ mA}</math> SNR: 110 dB Frame rate: 1-2000 fps Sampling rate: 25 Hz Temperature working range: -40-85 °C Power Consumption: <math>< 11 \mu\text{A}</math> at 25 fps Resolution: 20-bit ADC Dark-current noise <math>< 50\text{ pARMS}</math> Ambient level rejection >90 dB 120 Hz
Temperature	MAX 30208	Skin temperature (ST)	Accuracy: $\pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$ Sampling rate: 20 Hz

The questionnaires were designed on Google forms, where participants were invited to provide responses to inquiries pertinent to the research study objectives. In particular, three sections were present in the questionnaire:

- Multidomain comfort, including 5-point scale items [11] on thermal, visual, acoustic environments as well as on IAQ;
- Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (PANAS) [21];
- Presence questionnaire (7-point scale) [22].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

An example of the physiological and environmental data collected in the experimental campaign are reported in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4, respectively.

The measured values can be accessed also navigating through the BIM of the test room and selecting the corresponding placeholder, as visible in Fig. 1.

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

In this work the Authors have shown the preliminary results from the activities performed within the Horizon Europe project MULTICLIMACT, in particular in relation to the multidomain monitoring platform being developed to integrate physiological, environmental, and (in the near future) structural information collected on the ecosystem formed by building and its occupants.

The experimental tests will proceed in the next months; when the collected dataset is sufficiently wide, properly including physiological variability, both environmental and physiological data will be analysed to evaluate the correlation between each other as well as with the results from self-report surveys. In this way, the most relevant parameters in terms of well-being assessment will be selected for the creation of synthetic indices describing the occupants' health and well-being. More in detail, the acquired data will be processed using both algorithms embedded in the LIS platform and other ones developed in MATLAB/Python environments.

The final objective of data processing will be synthesizing indices related to the subject's well-being and health in the indoor living environment. To this aim, a few parameters highly correlated with the subject's comfort will be combined (or at least jointly considered) in synthetic indices to be included in the BIM of the test room for possible exploitation in terms of thermo-hygrometric control of the environment,

Fig. 3 Example of physiological data collected during the experimental campaign (LIS platform dashboard): a) HR, b) SpO₂, and c) ST.

Fig. 4 Example of environmental data collected during the experimental campaign (LIS platform dashboard): a) air T, b) RH, c) CO₂, d) PM_{2.5}, and e) VOC.

with the ultimate objective of optimizing both the subjects' well-being and the building energy consumption in a feedforward loop. Regarding well-being, also the physical activity level will be considered through the analysis of HR data; thermal comfort will be evaluated on the basis of both physiological parameters and survey results (in particular related to thermal perception).

The solution being implemented is highly interoperable and can be easily scaled according to the stakeholders' interests as well as to the intended use of the building being monitored; data security aspects are thoroughly considered to ensure their integrity and properly manage buildings exploiting wireless technologies [23]. Also, the application of Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning techniques will be evaluated in this context for predictive purposes on both environmental and physiological parameters as well as for comfort and well-being related aspects.

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